

OPEN Modeling *Clostridioides difficile* toxin pathogenesis and antiserum protection in an immunocompetent intestine-on-chip platform

Valentin D. Wegner¹, Maria Warschinke¹, Ibtissem Ben Brahim², Adrian Feile¹, Karen E. Huber² & Alexander S. Mosig¹✉

Clostridioides difficile (*C. difficile*) is a leading cause of nosocomial diarrhea and colitis, including severe pseudomembranous colitis, particularly following antibiotic-induced dysbiosis. The pathogenesis of *C. difficile* infection (CDI) is primarily driven by the action of two large exotoxins, toxin A (TcdA) and toxin B (TcdB), which compromise intestinal epithelial integrity and trigger strong mucosal inflammation. These toxins lead to the disassembly of epithelial junctions, immune cell infiltration, and release of pro-inflammatory mediators. Despite extensive research, mechanistic insight into *C. difficile*-host interactions and correlates of protection remain limited, in part due to the physiological constraints of conventional two-dimensional (2D) in vitro models. Here, we present a three-dimensional (3D) microphysiological Intestine-on-Chip (IoC) model as a dynamic and immunocompetent in vitro platform to study toxin-mediated pathogenesis and therapeutic interventions in CDI. In contrast to traditional static cell culture systems composed solely of epithelial monolayers, the immunocompetent IoC (i-IoC) model integrates Caco-2 C2BBE1 epithelial cells, primary human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), monocyte-derived macrophages, and circulating neutrophils (polymorphonuclear leukocytes, PMN) under continuous perfusion, thus more closely mimicking the tissue architecture and immune microenvironment of the human intestine. Upon stimulation with purified TcdA and TcdB, the i-IoC model exhibited toxin-specific disruption of epithelial junctional proteins, macrophage depletion, elevated cytokine secretion, and recruitment and transmigration of PMN, thereby replicating hallmark features of acute CDI. Notably, the model responded with higher sensitivity and biological complexity than static 2D cultures. Toxin-neutralizing antibody sera effectively attenuated these pathological responses, reducing both structural damage and inflammatory mediator release. Our findings demonstrate that the i-IoC model faithfully recapitulates key aspects of CDI pathophysiology, including epithelial damage, immune cell dynamics, and cytokine-driven inflammation. This platform offers a versatile and translationally relevant tool to study host–pathogen interactions and to evaluate preventive or therapeutic strategies aimed at mitigating *C. difficile* toxin (CDT)-mediated tissue injury.

Keywords *Clostridioides difficile* infection, Organ-on-chip, TcdA, TcdB, Neutralizing antibodies, Microphysiological system, Intestinal barrier

Clostridioides difficile (*C. difficile*) represents one of the major causes of nosocomial diarrhea and is associated with a range of diseases of different severities, primarily involving the colon^{1,2}. It is responsible for up to 15–20% of antibiotic-associated diarrhea and nearly all cases of pseudomembranous colitis³. *C. difficile* infections (CDIs) occur via the fecal–oral transmission of spores formed by this gram-positive, obligate anaerobic bacterium^{2,4}. Its endospores remain metabolically inactive but are aerotolerant and highly resistant to extreme temperatures, enzymatic degradation, oxidative agents, and many commonly used disinfectants⁵. These characteristics contribute to the persistence of *C. difficile* in clinical settings and highlight the importance of containment strategies in hospitals and long-term care facilities. Its resilience partly explains the challenges in developing effective treatment strategies and the ease of transmission within healthcare facilities^{4,6}. Additionally, a major

¹Institute of Biochemistry II, Jena University Hospital, Jena, Germany. ²Paul-Ehrlich-Institute, Federal Institute for Vaccines and Biomedicines, Langen, Germany. ✉email: alexander.mosig@med.uni-jena.de

clinical challenge is the high recurrence rate and the limited availability of effective preventive and therapeutic measures^{7–10}.

CDIs typically arise as a consequence of prolonged antibiotic treatment, which disrupts the gut microbiota and leads to intestinal dysbiosis^{9–11}. This dysregulation of the microbial ecosystem reduces colonization resistance and enables pathogens such as *C. difficile* to proliferate¹². The dysbiotic state further favors the germination of dormant *C. difficile* spores, often promoted by increased levels of primary bile acids, enabling the pathogen to proliferate and secrete its toxins^{5,10}. A potential clinical outcome is pseudomembranous colitis, an inflammatory condition of the colon marked by diarrhea and the formation of yellowish-white plaques (pseudomembranes) on the intestinal mucosa^{5,8}.

Treatment of CDI commonly involves antibiotics such as vancomycin, metronidazole, and fidaxomicin^{6,13,14}. Nevertheless, approximately one-third of patients experience reinfection or relapse following initial therapy^{7,13,14}. Furthermore, antibiotic treatment can alter the gut microbiome, thereby increasing the risk of recurrence and underscoring the urgent need for alternative preventive and therapeutic approaches¹³. Recent strategies focus on neutralizing *C. difficile* toxins (CDTs) using toxin-targeting antibodies, as anti-toxin antibody responses have been identified as correlates of protection, and such approaches help preserve microbial eubiosis^{15–18}. These approaches aim to protect the host epithelium and limit downstream inflammation without relying on microbiota-disruptive therapies.

The majority of CDI symptoms are mediated by the CDTs toxin A (TcdA) and toxin B (TcdB), which interfere with cellular functions and induce a strong inflammatory response in the intestinal epithelium^{14,19}. The mechanisms of CDT action include disruption of the intestinal barrier, cytokine release, and neutrophil infiltration^{19–22} (Fig. 1).

At the intestinal mucosa, TcdA and TcdB act as glucosyltransferases, which mainly modify and inactivate small GTPases such as Rac, Rho, and Cdc42, thereby inducing cytoskeletal disassembly, tight junction breakdown,

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the hallmarks of CDI. Following productive colonization of the colonic epithelium by *C. difficile* (green), the bacterium begins producing its toxins, TcdA (orange) and TcdB (blue). These toxins are the main virulence factors responsible for the pathogenesis and clinical manifestations of CDI^{14,19}. TcdA and TcdB act on different cell types, triggering a cascade of events: (1) inducing cytoskeletal changes that lead to a loss of epithelial barrier integrity, (2) causing epithelial cells (brown), macrophages (purple), and neutrophils (pink) to secrete inflammatory cytokines, and (3) promoting neutrophil infiltration into the infection site^{19–22}. These pathogenic mechanisms result in the formation of pseudomembranes, a hallmark feature of the inflamed intestinal mucosa caused by CDT-mediated tissue damage^{5,8,21}. Illustrations were created using BioRender.com.

cell rounding (cytopathic effect), and ultimately cell death^{14,19,23,24}. These structural disruptions compromise intestinal barrier integrity and promote translocation of microbial components, amplifying mucosal immune activation.

Simultaneously, due to the toxin-mediated activation of the pyrin inflammasome through sensing inactivated GTPases, monocyte and macrophage pyroptosis is triggered, which in turn causes further immune cell recruitment and cytokine release^{25–27}. In addition to their cytotoxic effects, TcdA and TcdB stimulate the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and IL-1 β ^{20,25}, and in this way promote neutrophil recruitment and infiltration at the site of infection^{19,21}. This inflammatory cascade contributes to the formation of fibrinous exudates in the intestinal mucosa^{10,19,21}. Collectively, these pathogenic processes result in the disruption of the colonic epithelium, increased intestinal permeability, and a self-reinforcing cycle of inflammation and tissue damage^{14,19,28}.

To facilitate a detailed study of host-microbe interactions, especially the complex processes and interactions occurring during CDI, we used an immunocompetent Intestine-on-Chip (i-IoC) model that mimics the *in vivo* tissue architecture, including its 3D structure, (multi)cellular composition, cellular interactions, and physiological function^{29–31} (Fig. 2B). The model exhibits the formation of villus- and crypt-like structures, a functional epithelial barrier, and mucosal immune components such as tissue-resident macrophages, along with circulating immune cells like neutrophils³¹. To compare it with well-established 2D models, the i-IoC model (Fig. 2B) was evaluated alongside a traditional cell culture insert model that features a polarized epithelial monolayer (Fig. 2A).

Organ-on-chip systems such as the i-IoC address the limitations of traditional static models by providing enhanced physiological complexity^{32,33}. A key advantage is the continuous perfusion that ensures a steady supply of nutrients while removing waste products, thereby effectively mimicking luminal flow dynamics in the gastrointestinal tract^{33,34}. The model incorporates intestinal epithelial cells and a vascular component in separate but interconnected chambers, along with both tissue-resident and circulating innate immune cells, emulating physiologically relevant conditions³⁵.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the 2D cell culture inserts and the (i-)IoC model. (A) Cross-section of the cell culture inserts and (B) schematic overview of the (i-)IoC model with a depiction of the integrated cells. Scalable biological complexity of the IoC model allows for the addition of immune cells, including monocyte-derived macrophages and circulating neutrophils (polymorphonuclear leukocytes, PMN) to generate the i-IoC. Illustrations were created using BioRender.com.

This allows, similarly to 2D cell culture inserts, monitoring of epithelial integrity and barrier disruption over time. Crucially, the integrated immune cells and the perfusion, only present in the microfluidic i-IoC, enable the generation of a more physiologically relevant 3D tissue architecture^{31,36}. This in turn leads to improved cellular differentiation, an increased sensitivity to microbial components, and the corresponding immune responses^{37,38}.

In this study, we used purified TcdA and TcdB of *C. difficile*, its main virulence factors, to model a CDI in vitro employing both static and dynamic culture systems using traditional cell culture inserts and an i-IoC platform. The advanced chip platform enables the integration of functional tissue-resident macrophages as well as circulating polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMNs), thereby increasing the model's complexity and enhancing its capacity to recapitulate key aspects of CDI more accurately. These additions allow the simulation of key immune responses, including cytokine signaling and PMN infiltration.

Finally, we explored the potential of neutralizing antibody sera against TcdA or TcdB, demonstrating a preventive strategy to mitigate toxin-induced tissue damage and the associated inflammatory responses. With that, our study provides insights into the translational value of advanced in vitro models for preclinical evaluation of CDI therapeutics.

Materials and methods

The general biochip handling, (i-)IoC build-up and processing, including the immunofluorescence staining and adjacent assays, was described before³⁹. Further, all cellular components together with the 3D tissue architecture were extensively characterized in detail in previous studies^{31,39}.

Ethics statement

This study was performed following the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Human peripheral blood was collected from healthy volunteers after receiving written informed consent. The blood donation protocol and use of blood for this study were approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of the Jena University Hospital (permission number 2207–01/08). Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) were collected under ethical approval 2020-1684, 3939-12/13 after donors provided written, informed consent.

Cell culture

HUVECs were isolated, expanded, and cryopreserved as previously described⁴⁰. After thawing, HUVECs were seeded at a density of 2×10^4 cells/cm² in Endothelial Cell Growth Medium (EC medium) MV (Promocell, Heidelberg, Germany) with a supplement mix provided by the manufacturer and 1% v/v of Penicillin/Streptomycin (GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany). The medium was exchanged twice weekly, and cells were cultured up to passage 3. Once the cells reached 80–90% confluency, they were harvested and used for subsequent experiments.

Caco-2 C2BBE1 cells were cultivated in C2 medium, DMEM high glucose (4.5 g/L) containing 10% v/v FBS, 1% v/v Glutamax, 1% v/v Sodium Pyruvate, 1% v/v MEM Non-Essential Amino Acids Solution, 0.2% v/v Holotransferin, and 0.2% v/v Gentamycin (all GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany). The cells were cultivated up to passage 35, and once they reached 80–90% confluency were harvested and used for experiments.

Human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) isolation

PBMC were isolated from healthy donors using a density gradient centrifugation⁴¹. In short, whole blood was collected in EDTA tubes (Sarstedt, Nümbrecht, Germany), diluted in a 1:1 ratio with Iso-buffer (PBS without Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺, (Capricorn Scientific, Ebsdorfergrund, Germany), 0.1% v/v BSA, 2 mM EDTA (both GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) to a final volume of 35 mL and layered on 15 mL of Histopaque density gradient medium (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). The density gradient centrifugation was performed at 800 g for 20 min at room temperature without a brake. The separated layer of immune cells was collected, washed with Iso-buffer, and centrifuged three times. The first centrifugation was performed at 200 g for 8 min at room temperature without brake, and twice at 150 g for 8 min at room temperature with brake to remove residual cells and blood components.

Isolated PBMCs were counted and seeded at a density of $1.25\text{--}1.5 \times 10^6$ cells/cm² in 6-well plates with 2 mL X-VIVO 15 medium (Lonza, Cologne, Germany) supplemented with 10% v/v autologous serum and 0.01% v/v M-CSF and GM-CSF (Peprotech, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany). The cells were incubated for 1 h at 5% CO₂ and 37 °C in a humidified incubator, washed twice with X-VIVO medium, and cultivated for an additional 24 h before being harvested with a Lidocaine/EDTA solution (4 mg/mL in PBS without Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺, 5 mM EDTA) (both GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany).

PMN isolation

PMNs were isolated from healthy donors using a density gradient centrifugation⁴². Whole blood collected in EDTA tubes (Sarstedt, Nümbrecht, Germany) was diluted in a 3:1 ratio with Iso-buffer (PBS without Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺, (Capricorn Scientific, Ebsdorfergrund, Germany)), 0.1% v/v BSA, 2 mM EDTA (both GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) to a final volume of 6 mL and layered on 5 mL of PolymorphPrep (PROGEN Biotechnik GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany). A density gradient centrifugation was performed at 500 g for 45 min at room temperature without a brake. The separated layer of PMN was collected, washed with Iso-buffer, and centrifuged at 400 g for 15 min at room temperature with a brake. The collected pellet was lysed with ACK lysing buffer (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) to remove the erythrocytes present. The PMNs were washed again at 600 g for 2 min at room temperature before being counted and used for perfusion in the biochip.

2D cell culture inserts

Caco-2 C2BBE1 cells were seeded into 24-well cell culture inserts with a pore diameter of 0.4 μm (Greiner Bio-one, Frickenhausen, Germany) with a cell density of $0.45 \times 10^5/\text{cm}^2$ in 300 μL C2 medium. The cells were cultivated for 21 days with regular medium exchange every 3 days⁴³.

Biochips

The biochips BC002 (Dynamic42 GmbH, Jena, Germany) consisted of a polybutylene terephthalate body, forming an upper and lower chamber, divided by a 12 μm thick polyethylene terephthalate (PET) membrane with a pore density of 1×10^5 pores/ cm^2 and a pore diameter of 8 μm (TRAKETCH Sabeu, Radeberg, Germany). The membrane's cell culture area comprises 2.18 cm^2 for the upper chamber and 1.62 cm^2 for the lower chamber⁴⁴.

3D intestine-on-chip model

Prior to cell seeding, the biochips were disinfected with 70% ethanol (VWR International GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany) and washed twice with MilliQ H₂O (Millipore, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). The membrane was coated using collagen IV (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL. HUVEC cells were seeded at a density of 0.35×10^5 cells/ cm^2 in EC medium with supplements, and 1% v/v Penicillin/Streptomycin mix into the upper chamber of the biochip. The cells were incubated at 5% CO₂ and 37 °C in a humidified incubator with a daily medium exchange. For the monocyte-containing model, the previously isolated PBMC-derived monocytes were added 48 h after HUVEC seeding on top of the HUVEC cells at a density of 0.85×10^5 cells/ cm^2 in EC medium containing supplements, autologous serum, and 1% v/v Penicillin/Streptomycin mix, and then cultivated for an additional 24 h. Subsequently, Caco-2 C2BBE1 cells were seeded on the opposite side of the membrane in the lower chamber of the biochip at a cell density of 0.42×10^6 cells/ cm^2 in C2 medium. The biochips were incubated upside down for 24 h to facilitate cell attachment to the membrane.

After the static build-up of the (i-)IoC, the biochips were connected to a peristaltic pump (ISMATEC, Wertheim, Germany) by attaching microfluidic medium reservoirs (microfluidic ChipShop, Jena, Germany) and platinum-cured silicon tubing (Dynamic42 GmbH, Jena, Germany) to the inlets of both chambers. The chips were perfused with circular flow in both chambers at 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, matching shear stress rates of 0.013 dyn/ cm^2 (0.0013 Pa) in the top chamber and 0.006 dyn/ cm^2 (0.0006 Pa) in the bottom chamber⁴⁴.

The (i-)IoC models were perfused for three days before adding 100 ng/mL Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) to the C2 medium on the Caco-2 C2BBE1 side. After 24 h of LPS in the system, the stimulations were performed. To perfuse the immune cells, the circular perfusion was switched to linear perfusion to avoid rupture of the neutrophils by the peristaltic pump. The vascular layer was perfused with 1×10^6 neutrophils in 3 mL of EC medium containing supplement, autologous serum, and 1% v/v Penicillin/Streptomycin mix, over the duration of one hour before switching back to circular perfusion.

Toxin neutralization and stimulation

TcdA and TcdB, together with the neutralizing antibody sera, were kindly provided by GSK (GSK, Rixensart, Belgium). TcdA and TcdB were purified from the culture of a *C. difficile* strain belonging to ribotype 087. TcdA and TcdB neutralizing antibodies were obtained by collecting serum from immunized animals with formalin-inactivated toxoid A or B, respectively. Titers determination was obtained by dosing against native toxins in an ELISA.

Toxins were diluted in C2 medium to the final concentrations of 50 ng/mL and 125 ng/mL for TcdA and 1.5 ng/mL and 12.5 ng/mL for TcdB, respectively. Neutralization was achieved by incubating toxins with neutralizing antibody sera at 37 °C for 1 h prior to use. The final toxins and neutralized toxins were used to stimulate the models for 24 or 72 h without restimulation.

Immunofluorescence staining

After 24 or 72 h of stimulation, the biochips were disconnected from the pumps. Both chambers were washed twice with cold PBS with Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ (Capricorn Scientific, Ebsdorfergrund, Germany), and then fixed with ice-cold methanol (Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany) for 15 min at -20 °C. After fixation, the chips were washed again with PBS, containing Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺, and stored at 4 °C until immunofluorescence staining.

Before staining the cells, the membranes were removed from the biochip using a scalpel. Membranes were incubated in permeabilization and blocking solution (0.1% v/v saponin (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and 3% v/v of normal donkey serum (BIOZOL, Eching, Germany) in PBS with Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺) for 30 min at room temperature. Cellular markers were stained with primary antibodies against CD31 (CellSignaling, Massachusetts, United States of America), E-cadherin (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), ZO-1 (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany), CD66b (BioLegend, San Diego, CA, USA), and CD68 (CellSignaling, Massachusetts, United States of America). The antibodies were diluted 1:100 in staining solution (0.1% v/v saponin and 3% v/v of normal donkey serum in PBS with Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺) and incubated overnight at 4 °C. On the next day, the membranes were washed three times in washing solution (0.1% v/v saponin in PBS with Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺) before incubating them with the corresponding secondary antibodies (all Jackson ImmunoResearch, St. Thomas' Place, United Kingdom) diluted 1:200 and DAPI (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) diluted 1:500 in staining solution for 30 min at room temperature. After 3 additional washing steps in washing solution, the membranes were mounted in fluorescence mounting medium (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) on glass slides (VWR International GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany) and covered by a glass coverslip (VWR International GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany).

Image acquisition and analysis

Immunofluorescence z-stack images were obtained with an Axio Observer 5, an ApoTome for optical sectioning, and a 20× objective, NA 0.8, all from Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH (Jena, Germany). Z-stacks were acquired with 1.5 μm steps from surface to membrane. The settings for excitation and emission wavelengths, as well as the exposure times, were as follows: AF647 (ex. 653 nm, em. 668 nm, 1000 ms), Cy3 (ex. 548 nm, em. 561 nm, 500 ms), EGFP (ex. 488 nm, em. 509 nm, 190 ms), DAPI (ex. 353 nm, em. 465 nm, 30 ms), Brightfield (20 ms). Z-stacks were imaged from the top of the sample to the membrane, with a thickness of 1.5 μm per layer, to ensure complete imaging of the whole tissue layer. Three separate images were taken per condition and staining panel. For the image quantification, predefined modules of the analysis software CellProfiler⁴⁵ were used to create a specific analysis pipeline for each marker, as published before⁴⁶.

Permeability assay

Barrier integrity of the cell culture inserts and the IoC model was assessed through fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-dextran measurements as described before³¹. FITC-dextran (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) with a size of 3–5 kDa in a concentration of 1 mg/mL in C2 medium (GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) without phenol red was used. In the cell culture inserts, the medium was replaced with fresh culture medium without phenol red, C2 medium (GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany), and 200 μL of FITC-dextran solution was added into the insert and incubated for 60 min at 5% CO₂ and 37 °C in a humidified incubator. For the IoC model, the culture medium in both cavities was replaced with fresh culture medium without phenol red, C2 medium (GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany), and EC medium (Promocell, Heidelberg, Germany). After that, 350 μL of FITC-dextran solution was added to the epithelial side containing the Caco-2 C2BBE1 cells and incubated for 60 min at 5% CO₂ and 37 °C in a humidified incubator under static conditions. The biochips were flipped such that the epithelial side faced upwards during the incubation. The supernatant of both models was collected and stored at 4 °C in the dark until the measurement. To determine the FITC-dextran concentration, a standard curve in a range of 0–500 μg/mL containing eight standard values in a serial 1:2 dilution was prepared, and the fluorescence was measured together with the samples at 517 nm in a black μClear 96-well plate (Greiner Bio-One, Frickenhausen, Germany).

The permeability coefficients P_{app} were calculated according to the following formula:

$$P_{app} = \frac{dQ}{dt} x \frac{1}{Ax C_0}$$

where dQ/dt is the permeability rate, A is the cell surface area, and C_0 is the initial FITC concentration. P_{app} values are expressed in cm/s.

LDH measurement

LDH was measured using the Cytotoxicity Detection Kit (Roche Diagnostics, Basel, Switzerland) according to the manufacturer's protocol. In short, the samples were centrifuged to remove cell debris and diluted 1:10 in PBS with Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ (Capricorn Scientific, Ebsdorfergrund, Germany). A standard curve was prepared over the range of 0–500 ng/mL, containing eight standard values in a serial 1:2 dilution. The reaction mix containing solutions 1 and 2 in a 1:50 ratio was prepared fresh, and 100 μL were added to each well containing standard or sample in a clear 96-well plate (Greiner Bio-One, Frickenhausen, Germany). After reaching a sufficient colour reaction, 50 μL of 1 M HCl (Sigma, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) was added per well to stop the reaction, followed by absorbance measurement at 490 nm.

Cytokine profiles

Cytokines from the supernatants of both models were measured using the LEGENDplex Human Inflammation Panel 1 (13-plex) assay (BioLegend, San Diego, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Supernatants were collected, centrifuged to remove cell debris, and stored at -80 °C until measurement. Samples were measured using a flow cytometer, LSRFortessa (BD Bioscience, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany). The resulting data was analyzed using the LEGENDplex Data Analysis Software.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of biological readouts was performed using GraphPad Prism v10.2.2 (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA). For the comparison of multiple conditions, a one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test was used. Statistical significance was included in the figures in the form of p-values. All p-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

To develop a 3D platform for studying CDT effects and potential protective measures, we refined a previously described i-IoC model³⁹ and directly compared it to standard 2D cell culture inserts. The conventional 2D inserts consist of a polarized monolayer of Caco2-C2BBE1 epithelial cells (Fig. 2A). In contrast, the i-IoC model features additional cells in two connected chambers. A vascular compartment lined with HUVECs and an epithelial compartment containing C2BBE1 cells is separated by a porous membrane that permits cell–cell contact and molecular exchange between sides. The inclusion of continuous perfusion in the i-IoC promotes a 3D outgrowth of the epithelium, improves barrier function, and enhances cellular differentiation of the C2BBE1 cells compared to static cell culture inserts, as previously shown by cross-sectional imaging revealing villus-like tissue protrusions of up to 150 μm in height^{31,36} (Fig. 2B). The i-IoC model is modular and scalable in complexity, allowing for the addition of tissue-resident macrophages as well as circulating PMNs that can be

perfused through the vascular compartment and infiltrate the intestinal tissue (Fig. 2). Using this multi-cellular i-IoC platform, we investigate the immune response upon exposure to CDTs TcdA and TcdB.

First, we compared the effects of purified TcdA and TcdB on static cell culture inserts versus the IoC system lacking tissue-resident immune cells (Fig. 3). Both models were treated for 24 h with TcdA (50 ng/mL and 125 ng/mL) or TcdB (1.5 ng/mL and 12.5 ng/mL) and analyzed for tissue and barrier integrity, as well as cytokine release. Distinct toxin-specific damage patterns were observed in both systems. TcdA exposure selectively disrupted the tight junction protein ZO-1 in a dose-dependent manner while leaving the adherence junction protein E-cadherin network largely intact. Further, TcdA-treated cells exhibited pronounced cell rounding. In contrast, TcdB caused extensive destruction of the epithelial cell layer, as evidenced by a marked reduction in junctional network area and fluorescence intensity of both ZO-1 and E-cadherin (Fig. 3A–C). Notably, in the static inserts, only the higher toxin doses (125 ng/mL TcdA; 12.5 ng/mL TcdB) produced significant damage to confluent cell layers, whereas in the IoC model, similar effects compromising tissue integrity were observed at lower doses (50 ng/mL TcdA; 1.5 ng/mL TcdB). This structural damage corresponded with the functional loss of barrier function and greater permeability of the intestinal tissue, demonstrated by a significant increase in FITC-dextran concentration (Fig. 3D). Furthermore, TcdA and TcdB stimulated IL-8 and LDH secretion. Similarly, this response was observed in 2D cell culture inserts only at high doses, whereas in the IoC, a strong IL-8 and LDH response was observed at lower doses (Fig. 3E–F). In the IoC model, none of the tested toxin concentrations caused detectable damage to the vascular lining (Suppl. Fig. 1). When TcdA and TcdB were administered together, their effects appeared to combine in an additive fashion without any indication of enhanced damage beyond their individual impacts (Suppl. Fig. 2).

In the next set of experiments, we evaluated toxin-neutralizing antibody sera as a potential correlate of protection. To account for the different sensitivities of the two systems, we applied the respective effective toxin doses for each model (higher doses for inserts and lower doses for the IoC model). TcdA and TcdB were pre-incubated for 1 h with toxin-specific neutralizing antisera and introduced into the cell culture models for 24 h of treatment. Neutralization of the toxins by antisera effectively prevented the toxin-induced tissue damage, preserving the epithelial junctional network and fluorescence signal recapitulated through ZO-1 and E-cadherin (Fig. 4A–B). In alignment with the maintenance of tissue integrity, its barrier function remained intact as demonstrated by the FITC-dextran permeability assay that showed no significant increase in dextran translocation when toxins were neutralized by antisera (Fig. 4C–D). Finally, IL-8 and LDH secretion were also significantly reduced by the presence of toxin-neutralizing antibody sera (Fig. 4C–D).

To further recapitulate the hallmarks of CDI, we next incorporated tissue-resident macrophages into the IoC model, generating the i-IoC. Macrophages markedly amplified the inflammatory response by significantly increasing IL-6 and IL-8 secretion upon toxin exposure (Fig. 5C) compared to IoCs without macrophages (Fig. 4D). However, toxin challenge of the i-IoC also led to a significant decrease of CD68⁺ macrophages (Fig. 5A–B).

Supplementation of the i-IoC with circulating neutrophils at the vascular lining further augmented cytokine release, with IL-6 and IL-8 levels reaching up to tenfold above baseline upon toxin treatment in the PMN-containing i-IoC model (Fig. 5E). Moreover, the challenge with CDTs led to adhesion and subsequent infiltration of PMN into the tissue, as reflected by increased adherent PMN on the vascular side and infiltrating PMN on the epithelial side (Fig. 5A, D). Consistent with earlier results, pre-incubation of the toxins with neutralizing antibody sera diminished immune cell-related toxin effects of tissue damage and prevented PMN adhesion and infiltration into the tissue (Fig. 5). In all conditions, the vascular layer was not affected by toxin challenge of the epithelial cell layer (Suppl. Fig. 1).

We further examined the long-term effects of toxin exposure in the i-IoC model (Fig. 6). I-IoC models were treated for 72 h with a single dose of TcdA or TcdB, or their neutralized counterparts. Prolonged toxin exposure exacerbated tissue damage (Fig. 6A–C) compared to the 24-h challenge, increasing cytokine release, permeability, and LDH secretion more than the 24-h exposure (Fig. 6D–G). In particular, TcdB-mediated tissue damage extended from the epithelial cell layer to the vascular lining (Fig. 6A, C), an effect not observed after 24 h of toxin exposure. Nevertheless, neutralisation of the toxins before exposure prevented tissue damage as measured by all markers.

Finally, the recovery potential of the i-IoC model was assessed (Fig. 7). I-IoC models were treated for 72 h with a single dose of TcdA or TcdB, followed by 72 h of perfusion without toxins. Perfusion with toxin-free culture medium facilitated tissue recovery only in the TcdB-treated models, not in the TcdA-treated models. This was recapitulated across all measured parameters, including tissue damage, permeability, cytokine release, and LDH release.

Discussion

In this study, we leveraged a microphysiological i-IoC model as a platform to investigate the tissue-specific effects of CDTs and evaluate correlates of protection. Compared to conventional 2D cell culture inserts, the i-IoC offers greater structural and cellular complexity, including perfused co-cultures of vascular and epithelial layers, as well as the integration of immune components such as macrophages and circulating neutrophils. Further, it more closely reflects the structural and functional features of the human intestinal mucosa. Under perfusion, the intestinal Caco-2 C2BBE1 epithelium develops villus- and crypt-like architectures and displays increased cellular differentiation, barrier formation, and functional maturity, traits which are consistent with *in vivo*-like intestinal tissue³¹. The model also allows stepwise addition of immune cells, making it highly adaptable for dissecting host–pathogen interactions with a focus on investigating immune-related responses.

All of these aforementioned advantages of the i-IoC model led to a significantly higher CDT sensitivity of the i-IoC model compared to the 2D inserts. Lower concentrations of TcdA and TcdB were sufficient to induce hallmark responses in the i-IoC model, including junctional protein loss and IL-8 secretion. In contrast, only

Fig. 3. Comparison of CDT effects on cell culture inserts and the IoC model. Both models were treated with two concentrations of TcdA (50 ng/mL, 125 ng/mL) or TcdB (1.5 ng/mL, 12.5 ng/mL) for 24 h. The epithelial cell layer was stained for (A) ZO-1 (tight junction, green) and E-cadherin (adherence junctions, yellow). Scale bars represent 50 μm . (B, C) Quantification of the junctional complex proteins ZO-1 and E-cadherin after treatment with TcdA (orange) and TcdB (blue). (D) Permeability of the tissue layer assessed by FITC-dextran permeation assay after toxin treatment. (E) Secretion of IL-8 induced by toxin treatment. (F) Assessment of cytotoxicity through LDH measurement. Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test. Bars represent mean \pm SD of 3 independent biological experiments ($n = 3$). Only p-values ≤ 0.05 are shown.

Fig. 4. Efficacy testing of toxin-neutralizing sera in cell culture inserts and the IoC model without immune cells. Both models were treated in two concentrations of TcdA (50 ng/mL, 125 ng/mL) or TcdB (1.5 ng/mL, 12.5 ng/mL) with and without neutralizing antibody sera for 24 h. The epithelial cell layer was stained for (A) ZO-1 (tight junction, green) and E-cadherin (adherence junctions, yellow). Scale bars represent 50 μm . (B) Quantification of the junctional complex proteins ZO-1 and E-cadherin. (C, D) Permeability of the tissue layer assessed by FITC-dextran permeation assay, secretion of IL-8, and assessment of cytotoxicity through LDH measurement induced by toxin treatment in both models. Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test. Bars represent mean \pm SD of 3 independent biological experiments ($n = 3$). Only p-values ≤ 0.05 are shown.

Fig. 5. Toxin effects in the i-IoC model with or without circulating PMN and neutralizing antibody sera. The models were exposed for 24 h to 50 ng/mL TcdA (orange) or 1.5 ng/mL TcdB (blue) with and without toxin-neutralizing antibody sera. **(A)** The immune cells were stained for CD68 (macrophages, green) and CD66b (PMN, red). Scale bars represent 50 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of CD68⁺ macrophages after toxin exposure with and without neutralizing antibody sera. **(C)** Secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 after toxin exposure and pre-treatment with neutralizing antibody sera. **(D)** Quantification of the CD66b⁺ PMNs in the vascular and epithelial tissue layer after toxin exposure with and without neutralizing antibody sera. **(E)** Secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 on both the vascular and epithelial side. Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test. Bars represent mean \pm SD of 3 independent biological experiments (n = 3). Only p-values \leq 0.05 are shown.

Fig. 6. Long-term toxin stimulation in the i-IoC model. Toxin exposure for 72 h with 50 ng/mL TcdA (orange) or 1.5 ng/mL TcdB (blue) with and without neutralizing antibody sera. **(A)** The epithelial cell layer was stained for ZO-1 (tight junction, green) and E-cadherin (adherence junctions, yellow), and the vascular layer was stained for VE-cadherin (vascular junctions, yellow) and CD68 (macrophages, green). **(B)** Quantification of the junctional complex proteins of the epithelial side (ZO-1 and E-cadherin). **(C)** Quantification of the junctional complex protein of the vascular lining (VE-cadherin) and macrophages (CD68). **(D)** Permeability of the tissue layer assessed by FITC-dextran permeation assay after toxin exposure with and without neutralizing antibody sera. **(E, F)** Secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 induced by toxin exposure with and without neutralizing antibody sera. **(G)** Assessment of cytotoxicity through LDH measurement. Scale bars represent 50 μm . Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test. Bars represent mean \pm SD of 3 independent biological experiments ($n = 3$). Only p -values ≤ 0.05 are shown.

Fig. 7. i-IoC model recovery. Toxin exposure for 72 h with 50 ng/mL TcdA (orange) or 1.5 ng/mL TcdB (blue) followed by 72 h of recovery without toxin present in the system. (A) The epithelial cell layer was stained for ZO-1 (tight junction, green) and E-cadherin (adherence junctions, yellow), and the vascular layer was stained for VE-cadherin (vascular junctions, yellow) and CD68 (macrophages, green). (B) Quantification of the junctional complex proteins of the epithelial side (ZO-1 and E-cadherin). (C) Quantification of the junctional complex protein of the vascular lining (VE-cadherin) and macrophages (CD68). (D) Permeability of the tissue layer assessed by FITC-dextran permeation assay after the recovery phase. (E, F) Secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 after the recovery phase. (G) Assessment of cytotoxicity through LDH measurement. Scale bars represent 50 μm . Statistical significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test. Bars represent mean \pm SD of 3 independent biological experiments (n = 3). Only p-values \leq 0.05 are shown.

high CDT concentrations had comparable effects in the static inserts. These results are in line with the literature showing increased sensitivity of Organ-on-Chip models over 2D cell culture systems. Morelli et al.³⁷ as well as Trietsch et al.³⁸ reported in their studies the increased sensitivity for toxins³⁷ and bacterial components³⁸ of perfused 3D model systems, compared to a static 2D Transwell model. This ability can be another advantage of microfluidic systems, as it helps to save costs and materials for substances in early development, where only a limited amount of material is available. Nevertheless, the use of cell culture inserts allows for easier upscaling of testing at lower costs and less hands-on time. It was further shown that this increased sensitivity correlates with improved cellular maturation induced by the perfusion-induced shear stress and associated cellular mechano-stimulation⁴⁷. Perfusion of the cells not only continuously exchanges the cell culture medium, supplying the cells with nutrition³⁹, but also circulates the toxins, leading to an increased toxin exposure. Finally, the 3D structure of the intestinal epithelial side offers a larger surface area for the toxins to reach the cells compared to a 2D monolayer, even when treated for a similar duration.

Both model systems were able to reproduce the toxin-specific tissue damage of toxins TcdA and TcdB. Hereby, the high concentrations used for the 2D inserts are on the higher end or even exceed physiological toxin concentrations reported in the literature. Even though the amount of toxins produced can vary strongly between different *C. difficile* strains⁴⁸, Pollock et al.^{49,50} reported TcdA and TcdB concentrations in diluted stool ranging from 0 to 100 ng/mL.

The toxin-specific damage was therefore defined as the key hallmark of CDI. Whereas TcdA led to a disruption of the tight junction protein ZO-1 and rounding of the cells, TcdB led to the complete loss of cells in the tissue layers. Even though most studies show a comparable effect of both toxins disrupting the epithelial barrier, the mode of action differs⁵¹. It was shown that TcdA particularly disrupts tight junctions more than TcdB in human intestinal stem cells and organoid models^{52,53}, which was suggested to be mediated through a TcdA-specific inactivation of the Ras family GTPase Rap, which is responsible for the regulation of cell–cell junctions⁵⁴. In line with this finding, TcdB has been shown to not only induce the caspase-dependent apoptosis pathway shared with TcdA but additionally induce glucosylation-independent cell necrosis⁵⁵, causing cell detachment⁵² and rapid cell death in human intestinal cell cultures and pig intestinal graft models⁵⁶. These observations initially led to the now obsolete classification of TcdA as an enterotoxin and TcdB as a cytotoxin, causing epithelial cell damage and increased mucosal permeability¹⁴. This explains the different effects visible in our study regarding tissue alterations and junctional complex proteins by TcdA and TcdB, while both have similar effects on loss of barrier integrity. Further, the rounding of the cells visible after TcdA treatment reflects the redistribution of the actin cytoskeleton within the cells, which leads to the described changes in cell morphology classified as cytopathic effect⁵⁷. This highlights the recent clinical observations that both toxins can act independently of each other and, if combined, contribute together to the disease progression and not sequentially^{58,59}. This is in line with the presented results for the combined toxins TcdA and TcdB, only showing an additive and not an enhanced effect on the i-IoC model.

Toxin stimulation of both the cell culture inserts and the IoC model induced the secretion of IL-8 from the epithelial cells, recapitulating earlier observations^{20,60}. The possibility to include further immune cells into the IoC model, such as monocyte-derived macrophages to generate the i-IoC, increased the amount of secreted cytokines of IL-6 and IL-8. This was defined within this study as the second hallmark of CDI and is typically observed during CDI^{61,62}. Herein, the monocytes are administered from the vascular side, migrate into the epithelial tissue, and differentiate into macrophages³¹. This allows the assessment of toxin effects beyond their influence on the epithelial cells. The toxin-induced cytokine secretion was further amplified by the presence of PMNs perfused on the vascular side. In summary, this inflammatory response mediated through the present immunocompetency closely mirrors the innate immune dynamics observed in CDI patient^{61,62}.

Besides the increase in cytokines, the toxin stimulation significantly decreases the number of macrophages present in the model. This observation matches previous reports on the induction of pyroptosis, an inflammatory type of programmed cell death, triggered by TcdA and TcdB. Pyroptosis is characterized by cell swelling and rupture of the plasma membrane, resulting in the release of cellular contents such as pro-inflammatory cytokines and danger-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). Mechanistically, it is a result of inflammasome activation through sensing of toxin-inactivated GTPases^{25,27}. This, in turn, can trigger further inflammation and recruitment of immune cells to the site of cell death¹⁴. The observed loss of CD68⁺ macrophages upon toxin exposure likely results from this pyroptotic cell death^{25,27}, which supports the use of the i-IoC model not only to study epithelial responses but also to capture immune cell dynamics and secondary inflammatory cascades.

PMN infiltration into the tissue upon toxin stimulation, yet another key feature of CDI pathology, was successfully recapitulated by the i-IoC model as well. In vivo, neutrophil influx contributes to pseudomembrane formation and colonic inflammation^{19,21}. The ability of the i-IoC platform to model PMN adhesion, transmigration, and interaction with tissue-resident immune cells provides valuable insights into host responses that are otherwise difficult to capture in static models.

Moreover, to capture more than the initial stages of tissue intoxication, long-term toxin exposure for 72 h was investigated. Toxin exposure up to 72 h led to progressive damage, extending beyond the epithelial layer to the vascular compartment, as evidenced by disruption of VE-cadherin. This underscores the utility of the i-IoC for modeling persistent inflammation and delayed tissue responses, conditions commonly seen in recurrent or prolonged CDI^{63,64}. These findings support the notion that epithelial-immune crosstalk amplifies tissue injury over time and highlight the value of extended culture durations in studying disease evolution.

To date, CDI treatment options are limited to antibiotic therapy or faecal microbiota transplantation^{6,14}, the latter remaining poorly standardised. This highlights the need for improved treatment approaches, such as neutralizing antibodies acting on one of the main virulence factors of *C. difficile*, its toxins^{14,19,63}. To date, only a few vaccine candidates exist for the prevention of CDI^{17,18}. In our study, both model systems were evaluated

	2D cell culture inserts	3D microfluidic i-IoC
Recapitulation of CDI hallmarks		
Disruption of the intestinal barrier	✓	✓ + (increased sensitivity at lower toxin concentration)
Cytokine release	✓	✓ + (aggravation in the immunocompetent model)
Neutrophil infiltration	X	✓
Complexity/physiological relevance		
Vascular component	(X)*	✓
(Tissue-resident) macrophages	(X)*	✓
Circulating neutrophils	X	✓
Cellular heterogeneity	low: single-layer enterocyte model	high: multi-cell type tissue
Sensitivity	low	high
Throughput and costs	high throughput comparably low costs	low throughput higher costs
Scalability of cellular complexity	low	high
Living bacterial infection model	possible and performed in both models ^{31,67,68} , however, the i-IoC holds great potential to provide a more physiologically relevant oxygen tension	
Oxygen gradient integration		
Long-term infection studies	X	✓

Table 1. Comparison of 2D cell culture inserts and the i-IoC model. Overview of the capability of both model systems in modeling CDI and their general performance and potential use as an in vitro platform. ✓ = capability present; ✓ + = enhanced capability; X = absent. * In theory, it is possible to seed cells on the opposite side of the cell culture insert membrane. However, still this would be a less physiological situation since there is no dynamic flow as in the i-IoC (static separation, diffusion-driven communication)^{31,69}.

as platforms to assess the efficacy of toxin-neutralizing antibody sera in preventing the key pathological features of CDI.

Of note, pre-incubation with neutralizing antibody sera effectively prevented CDT-dependent tissue damage and cytokine release in both models, as well as macrophage loss and PMN infiltration in the i-IoC model. However, the greater sensitivity of the i-IoC model allowed for testing at lower toxin and antibody concentrations, conserving valuable reagents.

The experiments were performed with polyclonal antibodies as a proof-of-concept study to evaluate the feasibility of testing neutralizing antibodies in a cost-efficient manner. The results presented show the feasibility of using the i-IoC model for testing clinically relevant monoclonal antibodies. For such antibodies, the i-IoC model demonstrated higher sensitivity, which is particularly advantageous, as typically only limited amounts of material are available during early development. Moreover, the i-IoC model can be used as a well-defined in vitro platform to test for antibody functionality and neutralising potential. However, it should be noted that the polyclonal nature of the antisera used may not fully recapitulate the binding kinetics and epitope specificity of monoclonal antibodies, and further validation with clinically advanced monoclonal candidates will be required to fully assess the platform's translational potential.

Our results validate the use of the i-IoC platform as a preclinical screening tool for toxin-targeted therapies, including antibodies and vaccines^{14,19,63}. The model may thus support refinement and reduction of in vivo studies by providing a physiologically relevant yet controlled in vitro alternative.

Furthermore, removal of toxins from the i-IoC models revealed toxin-specific differences in the recovery capacity of the tissue layers. TcdA-treated tissues showed no recovery after 72 h of toxin-free perfusion, whereas TcdB-treated tissues exhibited substantial regeneration of the epithelial layer. This differential recovery likely reflects the distinct mechanisms of cell death and junction disruption induced by each toxin. TcdA, unlike TcdB, glycosylates Rap family GTPases in addition to Rho, Rac, and Cdc42⁵⁴, thereby directly interfering with cell–cell junction regulation through Rap-dependent pathways. Moreover, TcdA has been shown to attenuate Wnt/ β -catenin signaling in intestinal epithelial cells⁶⁵, a pathway essential for intestinal stem cell maintenance and epithelial renewal⁶⁶. Together, the irreversible inactivation of junction-regulatory GTPases and the suppression of proliferative signaling may account for the inability of TcdA-damaged tissues to regenerate. In contrast, TcdB at the concentrations used in this study primarily induces glucosyltransferase-independent necrotic cell death^{52,55} characterized by cell detachment rather than disruption of the junctional regulatory machinery in surviving cells. The bimodal cytotoxicity of TcdB, which involves apoptosis at low concentrations and necrosis at higher concentrations⁶⁶, results in physical loss of affected cells while leaving adjacent, non-intoxicated cells with an intact capacity for proliferation and tissue repair. These findings demonstrate the utility of the i-IoC platform for distinguishing toxin-specific pathomechanisms and for assessing the regenerative potential of the intestinal tissue following defined insults.

In summary, both the 2D insert and the i-IoC model are capable of reproducing hallmark features of CDI. However, the i-IoC provides superior physiological relevance, modularity, and sensitivity, enabling the integration of complex multicellular interactions. This positions the model as a promising platform for mechanistic studies and therapeutic testing. Future extensions could include histological analysis of pseudomembrane-like structures, exploration of PMN-endothelial interactions, and incorporation of live microbial cultures under defined oxygen gradients. To provide a comparative overview, Table 1 summarizes the key differences between 2D cell culture

inserts and the i-IoC model. The table highlights the enhanced sensitivity and biological relevance of the i-IoC platform, particularly in modeling complex immune interactions and long-term CDI pathophysiology.

Despite these advances, the study has some limitations that need to be acknowledged. The current model relies on the Caco-2 C2BBE1 cell line, which, while widely used and well-characterized, does not fully recapitulate the cellular heterogeneity of the native intestinal epithelium, including goblet cells, Paneth cells, and enteroendocrine cells. Future iterations could incorporate primary human intestinal epithelial cells or patient-derived organoids to enhance physiological fidelity. Furthermore, the toxin-based approach used here, while enabling controlled mechanistic studies, does not capture the full complexity of a live *C. difficile* infection, including bacterial colonization, sporulation, and microbiome interactions. Finally, the current immune compartment is limited to innate immune cells. The inclusion of adaptive immune components, such as T cells, would further expand the model's utility for studying vaccination responses and long-term immunological memory.

Ultimately, by integrating epithelial, vascular, and immune components under dynamic flow, the i-IoC model represents a versatile infection model. It offers new opportunities to study host–pathogen interactions in a more human-relevant context. It further supports the development of personalized treatment strategies, particularly when combined with patient-derived epithelial or immune cells and clinical isolates of *C. difficile*. As antibiotic resistance and treatment failures continue to challenge CDI management, such models will be instrumental in advancing the next generation of therapeutics and vaccines.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Received: 20 October 2025; Accepted: 10 March 2026

Published online: 17 March 2026

References

- Di Bella, S. et al. Clostridioides difficile infection: History, epidemiology, risk factors, prevention, clinical manifestations, treatment, and future options. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* **37**, e0013523 (2024).
- Buddle, J. E. & Fagan, R. P. Pathogenicity and virulence of Clostridioides difficile. *Virulence* **14**, 2150452 (2023).
- Nasiri, M. J. et al. Clostridioides (Clostridium) difficile infection in hospitalized patients with antibiotic-associated diarrhea: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Anaerobe* **50**, 32–37 (2018).
- Finn, E., Andersson, F. L. & Madin-Warburton, M. Burden of Clostridioides difficile infection (CDI)—A systematic review of the epidemiology of primary and recurrent CDI. *BMC Infect. Dis.* **21**, 456 (2021).
- Shen, A., Edwards, A. N., Sarker, M. R. & Paredes-Sabja, D. Sporulation and germination in clostridial pathogens. *Microbiol. Spectr.* **7**(6), 10–128 (2019).
- Smits, W. K., Lyras, D., Lacy, D. B., Wilcox, M. H. & Kuijper, E. J. Clostridium difficile infection. *Nat. Rev. Dis. Primers.* **2**, 16020 (2016).
- Feuerstadt, P., Theriault, N. & Tillotson, G. The burden of CDI in the United States: A multifactorial challenge. *BMC Infect. Dis.* **23**, 132 (2023).
- Cymbal, M., Chatterjee, A., Baggott, B. & Auron, M. Management of Clostridioides difficile infection: Diagnosis, treatment, and future perspectives. *Am. J. Med.* **137**, 571–576 (2024).
- Kelly, C. R. & Allegretti, J. R. Review article: Gastroenterology and Clostridium difficile infection: Past, present, and future. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* **77**, S463–S470 (2023).
- Czepiel, J. et al. Clostridium difficile infection: Review. *Eur. J. Clin. Microbiol. Infect. Dis.* **38**, 1211–1221 (2019).
- Rupnik, M., Wilcox, M. H. & Gerding, D. N. Clostridium difficile infection: New developments in epidemiology and pathogenesis. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **7**, 526–536 (2009).
- Mougiou, D., Gioula, G., Skoura, L., Anastasopoulou, C. & Kachrimanidou, M. Insights into the interaction between clostridioides difficile and the gut microbiome. *J. Personal. Med.* **15**(3), 94 (2025).
- Crowther, G. S. & Wilcox, M. H. Antibiotic therapy and Clostridium difficile infection—primum non nocere—first do no harm. *Infect. Drug Resist.* **8**, 333–337 (2015).
- Pourliotopoulou, E., Karampatakis, T. & Kachrimanidou, M. Exploring the toxin-mediated mechanisms in clostridioides difficile infection. *Microorganisms.* **12**(5), 1004 (2024).
- Mullard, A. FDA approves antitoxin antibody. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **15**, 811 (2016).
- Wilcox, M. H. et al. Bezlotoxumab for prevention of recurrent Clostridium difficile infection. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **376**, 305–317 (2017).
- de Bruyn, G. et al. Safety, immunogenicity, and efficacy of a Clostridioides difficile toxoid vaccine candidate: a phase 3 multicentre, observer-blind, randomised, controlled trial. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* **21**(2), 252–262 (2021).
- Donskey, C. J. et al. CLOVER (clostridium difficile vaccine efficacy trial) study: A phase 3, randomized trial investigating the efficacy and safety of a detoxified toxin A/B vaccine in adults 50 years and older at increased risk of Clostridioides difficile infection. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* **79**, 1503–1511 (2024).
- Shin, J. H., Chaves-Olarte, E. & Warren, C. A. Clostridium difficile infection. *Emerging Infect.* **10**(20), 265–294 (2016).
- Xu, Q. et al. Clostridium difficile toxin B-induced colonic inflammation is mediated by the FOXO3/PPM1B pathway in fetal human colon epithelial cells. *Am. J. Transl. Res.* **12**, 6204–6219 (2020).
- Shen, A. Clostridium difficile toxins: Mediators of inflammation. *J. Innate Immun.* **4**, 149–158 (2012).
- Solomon, K. The host immune response to Clostridium difficile infection. *Ther. Adv. Infect. Dis.* **1**, 19–35 (2013).
- Carter, G. P., Awad, M. M., Kelly, M. L., Rood, J. I. & Lyras, D. TcdB or not TcdB: a tale of two Clostridium difficile toxins. *Future Microbiol.* **6**, 121–123 (2011).
- Liu, Z. et al. Structural basis for selective modification of Rho and Ras GTPases by Clostridioides difficile toxin B. *Sci. Adv.* **7**(43), 4582 (2021).
- Donlan, A. & Petri, W. A. Jr. The inflammasome and type-2 immunity in Clostridium difficile infection. *Clin. Colon Rectal Surg.* **33**, 67–72 (2020).
- Man, S. M., Karki, R. & Kanneganti, T. D. Molecular mechanisms and functions of pyroptosis, inflammatory caspases and inflammasomes in infectious diseases. *Immunol. Rev.* **277**, 61–75 (2017).
- Saavedra, P. H. V. et al. Apoptosis of intestinal epithelial cells restricts Clostridium difficile infection in a model of pseudomembranous colitis. *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 4846 (2018).
- Bratkovic, T. et al. New treatment approaches for Clostridioides difficile infections: Alternatives to antibiotics and fecal microbiota transplantation. *Gut Microbes* **16**, 2337312 (2024).

29. Kapalczynska, M. et al. 2D and 3D cell cultures—A comparison of different types of cancer cell cultures. *Arch. Med. Sci.* **14**, 910–919 (2018).
30. Reardon, S. “Organs-on-chips” go mainstream. *Nature* **523**, 266 (2015).
31. Maurer, M. et al. A three-dimensional immunocompetent intestine-on-chip model as in vitro platform for functional and microbial interaction studies. *Biomaterials* **220**, 119396 (2019).
32. Aziz, A. U. et al. The role of microfluidics for organ on chip simulations. *Bioengineering* **4**(2), 39 (2017).
33. Bhatia, S. N. & Ingber, D. E. Microfluidic organs-on-chips. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **32**, 760–772 (2014).
34. Hofer, M. & Lutolf, M. P. Engineering organoids. *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **6**, 402–420 (2021).
35. Bein, A. et al. Microfluidic organ-on-a-chip models of human intestine. *Cell. Mol. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* **5**, 659–668 (2018).
36. Kim, H. J. & Ingber, D. E. Gut-on-a-chip microenvironment induces human intestinal cells to undergo villus differentiation. *Integr. Biol.* **5**, 1130–1140 (2013).
37. Morelli, M., Cabezuolo Rodriguez, M. & Queiroz, K. A high-throughput gut-on-chip platform to study the epithelial responses to enterotoxins. *Sci. Rep.* **14**, 5797 (2024).
38. Trietsch, S. J. et al. Membrane-free culture and real-time barrier integrity assessment of perfused intestinal epithelium tubes. *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 262 (2017).
39. Feile, A., Wegner, V. D., Raasch, M. & Mosig, A. S. Immunocompetent intestine-on-chip model for analyzing gut mucosal immune responses. *JoVE J Visual Exp.* **207**, e66603 (2024).
40. Raasch, M. et al. Microfluidically supported biochip design for culture of endothelial cell layers with improved perfusion conditions. *Biofabrication* **7**, 015013 (2015).
41. Mosig, S. et al. Different functions of monocyte subsets in familial hypercholesterolemia: Potential function of CD14+ CD16+ monocytes in detoxification of oxidized LDL. *FASEB J.* **23**, 866–874 (2009).
42. Fischer, J., Gresnigt, M. S., Werz, O., Hube, B. & Garscha, U. *Candida albicans*-induced leukotriene biosynthesis in neutrophils is restricted to the hyphal morphology. *FASEB J.* **35**, e21820 (2021).
43. Darling, N. J., Mobbs, C. L., Gonzalez-Hau, A. L., Freer, M. & Przyborski, S. Bioengineering novel in vitro co-culture models that represent the human intestinal mucosa with improved Caco-2 structure and barrier function. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **8**, 992 (2020).
44. Kaden, T. et al. Modeling of intravenous caspofungin administration using an intestine-on-chip reveals altered *Candida albicans* microcolonies and pathogenicity. *Biomaterials* **307**, 122525 (2024).
45. Stirling, D. R. et al. CellProfiler 4: Improvements in speed, utility and usability. *BMC Bioinformatics* **22**, 433 (2021).
46. Wegner, V. D. et al. Short-chain fatty acids modulate anti-ROR1 CAR T-cell function and exhaustion in an intestinal adenocarcinoma-on-chip model. *Adv. Healthcare Mater.* **14**(13), 2405003 (2025).
47. Fois, C. A. M., Schindeler, A., Valtchev, P. & Dehghani, F. Dynamic flow and shear stress as key parameters for intestinal cells morphology and polarization in an organ-on-a-chip model. *Biomed. Microdevices* **23**, 55 (2021).
48. Dong, Q. et al. Virulence and genomic diversity among clinical isolates of ST1 (BI/NAP1/027) *Clostridioides difficile*. *Cell Rep.* **42**, 112861 (2023).
49. Pollock, N. R. et al. Comparison of *Clostridioides difficile* stool toxin concentrations in adults with symptomatic infection and asymptomatic carriage using an ultrasensitive quantitative immunoassay. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* **68**, 78–86 (2019).
50. Alonso, C. D. et al. Ultrasensitive and quantitative toxin measurement correlates with baseline severity, severe outcomes, and recurrence among hospitalized patients with *Clostridioides difficile* infection. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* **74**, 2142–2149 (2022).
51. Aktories, K. & Just, I. Clostridial Rho-inhibiting protein toxins. *Curr. Top. Microbiol. Immunol.* **291**, 113–145 (2005).
52. Mileto, S. J. et al. *Clostridioides difficile* infection damages colonic stem cells via TcdB, impairing epithelial repair and recovery from disease. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **117**, 8064–8073 (2020).
53. Leslie, J. L. et al. Persistence and toxin production by *Clostridium difficile* within human intestinal organoids result in disruption of epithelial paracellular barrier function. *Infect. Immun.* **83**, 138–145 (2015).
54. Pruiett, R. N. et al. Structural determinants of *Clostridium difficile* toxin A glucosyltransferase activity. *J. Biol. Chem.* **287**, 8013–8020 (2012).
55. Peritore-Galve, F. C. et al. Glucosyltransferase-dependent and independent effects of *Clostridioides difficile* toxins during infection. *PLoS Pathog.* **18**, e1010323 (2022).
56. Chumbler, N. M. et al. *Clostridium difficile* Toxin B causes epithelial cell necrosis through an autoproducting-independent mechanism. *PLoS Pathog.* **8**, e1003072 (2012).
57. Chaves-Olarte, E. et al. R-Ras glucosylation and transient RhoA activation determine the cytopathic effect produced by Toxin B variants from Toxin A-negative strains of *Clostridium difficile*. *J. Biol. Chem.* **278**, 7956–7963 (2003).
58. Yoshino, Y. et al. *Clostridium difficile* flagellin stimulates Toll-like receptor 5, and Toxin B promotes flagellin-induced chemokine production via TLR5. *Life Sci.* **92**, 211–217 (2013).
59. Nezhadi, J., Lahouty, M., Rezaee, M. A. & Fadaee, M. *Clostridium difficile* as a potent trigger of colorectal carcinogenesis. *Discov. Oncol.* **16**, 910 (2025).
60. Hansen, A. et al. The P2Y6 receptor mediates *Clostridium difficile* toxin-induced CXCL8/IL-8 production and intestinal epithelial barrier dysfunction. *PLoS ONE* **8**, e81491 (2013).
61. Yu, H. et al. Cytokines are markers of the clostridium difficile-induced inflammatory response and predict disease severity. *Clin. Vaccine Immunol.* **24**(8), e00037-e117 (2017).
62. Hamo, Z., Azrad, M., Nitzan, O. & Peretz, A. Characterization of the immune response during infection caused by *Clostridioides difficile*. *Microorganisms* <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms7100435> (2019).
63. Berry, P. & Khanna, S. Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* infection: Current clinical management and microbiome-based therapies. *BioDrugs* **37**, 757–773 (2023).
64. Negrut, N. et al. Risk factors associated with recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* infection. *Healthcare* <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare8030352> (2020).
65. Bezerra Lima, B. et al. *Clostridium difficile* toxin A attenuates Wnt/beta-catenin signaling in intestinal epithelial cells. *Infect. Immun.* **82**, 2680–2687 (2014).
66. Chumbler, N. M., Farrow, M. A., Lapiere, L. A., Franklin, J. L. & Lacy, D. B. *Clostridium difficile* toxins TcdA and TcdB cause colonic tissue damage by distinct mechanisms. *Infect. Immun.* **84**, 2871–2877 (2016).
67. Grassart, A. et al. Bioengineered human organ-on-chip reveals intestinal microenvironment and mechanical forces impacting *Shigella* infection. *Cell Host Microbe* **26**, 435–444 e4 (2019).
68. Jalili-Firoozinezhad, S. et al. A complex human gut microbiome cultured in an anaerobic intestine-on-a-chip. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **3**, 520–531 (2019).
69. Kim, H. J., Huh, D., Hamilton, G. & Ingber, D. E. Human gut-on-a-chip inhabited by microbial flora that experiences intestinal peristalsis-like motions and flow. *Lab. Chip* **12**, 2165–2174 (2012).

Acknowledgements

We thank GSK for providing the toxins TcdA and TcdB as well as the neutralizing antibody sera. A.S.M. has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007799 (Inno4Vac). This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 re-

search and innovation program and EFPIA. A.S.M. further acknowledges funding by the BMBF program Photonics Research Germany (FKZ:13N15713, 13N15716), which is integrated into the Leibniz Center for Photonics in Infection Research (LPI). This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy (EXC 2051, Project-ID 390713860).

Author contributions

V.D.W. and M.W. contributed equally and performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and contributed to writing the manuscript. I.B.B. performed transwell experiments. A.F. contributed to the experimental setup and model characterization. K.E.H. and A.S.M. conceived and supervised the study, acquired funding, and wrote the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL. A.S.M. acknowledges funding by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft under Germany's Excellence Strategy—EXC 2051, Grant Number: 390713860 and by the BMFT program Photonics Research Germany (FKZ: 13N15716), which is integrated into the Leibniz Centre for Photonics in Infection Research (LPI). The LPI initiated by Leibniz-IPHT, Leibniz-HKI, UKJ, and FSU Jena is part of the BMBF national roadmap for research infrastructures. K.E.H. and A.S.M. have received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007799 (Inno4Vac). This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program and EFPIA.

Declarations

Competing interests

A.S.M. holds equity in Dynamic42 GmbH. A.S.M. consults Dynamic42 GmbH. The remaining authors declare no conflict of interest.

Additional information

Supplementary Information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-026-44170-8>.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to A.S.M.

Reprints and permissions information is available at www.nature.com/reprints.

Publisher's note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

© The Author(s) 2026